

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

EMAIL

esfc.lisbon@chemistry.pt

WEBSITE

21-esfc-lisbon.events.chemistry.pt

Book of Abstracts

21st European Symposium on Fluorine Chemistry

ESFC LISBON 2025

Lisbon, 3 – 9 August 2025

ISBN 978-989-8124-47-0

9 789898 124470

13:10 – 13:25 **TOWARDS A NEW DIRECT METHOD FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF ARYL DIFLUOROALKYL ETHERS FROM THE DIFLUOROMETHOXY (-OCHF₂) MOIETY**

Oral **Guillaume Siegel**, CNRS - Université de Strasbourg, France

PARALLEL SESSION I – INORGANIC CHEMISTRY & COMPUTATIONAL CHEMISTRY

Room: 3A

Chair: Beate Kocsch, Freie University of Berlin, Germany

11:15 – 11:35 **CHEMISTRY OF MOF₅ AND MOOF₃**

IL **Michael Gerken**, University of Lethbridge, Canada

11:35 – 11:55 **METAL FLUORIDE COMPLEXES AS FUNCTIONAL, STRUCTURE-DIRECTING BUILDING BLOCKS IN MOLECULAR MAGNETISM AND BEYOND**

IL **Jesper Bendix**, University of Copenhagen, Denmark

11:55 – 12:10 **PHYSICOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF CHEMICAL CAPACITORS FEATURING FLUORINE-RICH OXIDIZERS AND SEPARATORS**

Oral **Łukasz Wolański**, University of Warsaw, Poland

12:10 – 12:25 **NOVEL X_E-N AND X_E-O BONDED CATIONS: FORMATION, STRUCTURE, AND REACTIVITY**

Oral **Kristian Radan**, Jozef Stefan Institute, Slovenia

12:25 – 12:40 **FROM COPPER TO LANTHANIDES: UNIQUE COMPLEXES WITH WEAKLY BOUND LIGANDS AND STABILIZED BY WEAKLY COORDINATING ANIONS**

Oral **Przemysław J. Malinowski**, Centre of New Technologies, University of Warsaw, Poland

12:40 – 12:55 **DECODING THE FLUOROUS EFFECT WITH IR SPECTROSCOPY**

Oral **Ruben Cruz**, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

12:55 – 13:10 **SUPERCONDUCTIVITY IN LITHIUM HYDRIDE LAYER ENHANCED BY FLUORIDE SUBSTRATES**

Oral **Piotr Szkudlarek**, University of Warsaw, Poland

PARALLEL SESSION I – CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN SPONSORED BY MAR2PROTECT

Room: 3B

Chair: Manuel M. Piñeiro, Universidade de Vigo, Spain

11:15 – 11:30 **IMPLEMENTING LIVINGLABS FOR GROUNDWATER PROTECTION: MAR2PROTECT EXPERIENCES IN EUROPE AND AFRICA**

IL **Uta Wehn**, IHE Delft Institute for Water Education, The Netherlands

11:30 – 11:45 **NATURAL WETLANDS AS NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS TO REMOVE POLLUTANTS AND PROMOTE THE GOOD QUALITY OF ESTUARINE SURFACE WATER**

IL **C. Marisa R. Almeida**, CIIMAR, Porto University, Portugal

11:45 – 12:00 **REAL-TIME BIOMONITORING OF EMERGING CONTAMINANTS IN WATER RESOURCES**

IL **Gideon Wolfaardt**, Stellenbosch University, South Africa

Monday

ESFC LISBON
21st European
Symposium on
Fluorine Chemistry

<https://21-esfc-lisbon.events.chemistry.pt/>

Natural Wetlands as Nature-based Solutions to Remove Pollutants and Promote the Good Quality of Estuarine Surface Water

C. Marisa R. Almeida^{1,2} Vânia Freitas,¹ Loreto Garcia,¹ Jacinto Cunha,¹ Sandra Ramos^{1,2}*

(1) CIIMAR - Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research of the University of Porto, Matosinhos, Portugal

(2) Sciences Faculty, Porto University, Porto, Portugal

**e-mail: calmeida@ciimar.up.pt*

Natural wetlands, including estuarine saltmarshes, have long been used as uncontrolled discharge sites for different sources of wastewater due to their recognised ability to improve water quality. Saltmarsh plants and their associated microbial communities, along with their sediments, play an important role in the removal of contaminants. Plant roots and rhizomes can act as a net that traps thin sediments leading to a decrease in water flow and turbulence in these areas, resulting in the retention of pollutants in sediments and subsequent accumulation/degradation by marsh vegetation and associated rhizosphere microbial communities. Saltmarsh plants and their rhizosphere microbial communities have proven to be phytoremediation agents for the retention and/or removal of several of these contaminants. Estuarine saltmarshes can therefore, act as filters for pollutants released from different anthropogenic activities, including agricultural, industrial and domestic discharges, as many urban areas are located near or within estuaries. Moreover, aquaculture facilities and ports can contribute to the anthropogenic pressures in estuaries. Hence, different contaminants can be found in estuarine environments, namely metals, endocrine disrupting chemicals, pesticides and petroleum hydrocarbons, as well as contaminants of emergent concern (CECs) like pharmaceuticals. Using the Lima estuary (Northern Portugal, Figure 1) as a case study, this presentation will show the potential of saltmarshes to remove various contaminants (e.g., metals, pharmaceuticals and other CECs) from the aquatic environment, preventing them from spreading in the area and reaching coastal areas and/or eventually contaminating the underlying aquifers. The presentation will also outline the innovative approach that is being implemented in the Lima estuary that combines the phytoremediation potential of saltmarsh halophytes with pilot revegetation efforts to enhance the uptake and/or biodegradation of contaminants present in sediments and surface water (Figure 1). All these activities are being developed in the framework of the Mar2Protect EU project. Results will showcase the potential of saltmarsh ecosystems in promoting sustainable water management.

Figure 1. Lima estuary and re-vegetation site.

Acknowledgments: To project Mar2Protect (GA N^o 101082048) funded by European Union Horizon Europe.

21st European Symposium on Fluorine Chemistry
3-9 August 2025
esfc.lisbon@chemistry.pt

DIAMOND

feuga fundación
empresa
universidad
gallega

 European
Recycling
Platform

GOLD

F-select GmbH
*selective fluorination
smart chemistry*

 magritek
Benchtop NMR Spectroscopy

 apria

COMEAU

 DEXYAN
帝延国际

 PFASUIKI

thermo**scientific**
UNICAM
www.thermounicam.pt

SILVER

 EXFLUOR
research corp.

 ambigroup
Reciclagem, S.A.

 WonderStatus
Soluções de Laboratório

 BASF
We create chemistry

OTHER SUPPORT

Interreg Sudoe Co-funded by
the European Union

 **Life 4
F-gases**

AGC
Your Dreams, Our Challenge

 **Chemistry
Europe**
European Chemical
Societies Publishing

ALERT-PFAS

 ELSEVIER

**MAR2
PROTECT**

**JOURNAL OF
FLUORINE
CHEMISTRY**

**Porto.
Águas
e Energia
do Porto**

 VEOLIA

 **ROYAL SOCIETY
OF CHEMISTRY**

 gradiva

 Thieme

F Fluorinova
CONSULTING

LABOR
SPIRIT, Lda.

mtb
PRECISION TECHNOLOGY

INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT

**LAQV
requimte**
LABORATÓRIO ASSOCIADO
PARA A QUÍMICA VERDE

Nova
FACULDADE DE
CIÊNCIAS E TECNOLOGIA

 SOCIEDADE PORTUGUESA DE QUÍMICA